

Constitution of Corchoritin—a New Crystalline Bitter from Jute-seeds. Part I.*

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The occurrence of a second bitter which accompanies corchorin in alcoholic extract of *Corchorus capsularis* has been noted in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 905). A small quantity of the impure substance has been isolated by fractional crystallisation of the mother-liquor of corchorin and further work shows that it is, in reality, a mixture, and the material could be separated into a chloroform-soluble and a water-soluble portion. The chloroform extract after repeated concentration and precipitation with petroleum ether, and finally after several crystallisations from alcohol (animal charcoal) gave a product crystallising in long prisms which melted with effervescence at 218-20° after preliminary softening. The anhydrous product had the formula $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ and $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -35.1^\circ$ in 96 per cent. alcohol.

As the properties of the compound do not agree with those of any known compound of the same empirical formula, it is considered to be a new compound and has been termed corchoritin. The colour reactions and other properties of this substance are such as to suggest its identity with corchorin but unlike corchorin this new compound does not yield any hexose on hydrolysis and no furfural or methyl furfural is obtained from the substance on distillation with 12 per cent. hydrochloric acid and the failure of the Keller-Kiliani test shows the absence of any desoxy sugar. An interesting fact to which attention may be directed is that whereas corchorin is *dextrorotatory*, corchoritin is *laevorotatory*.

It seems to be a member of the homologous series having the general formula $C_nH_{2n-6}O_3$ to which corchogenin, the aglucone of corchorin belongs. Its intimate relationship with corchogenin is made more striking by its common occurrence with the parent substance of corchogenin in the same plant.

The presence of considerable amounts of reducing sugar in jute seeds considered in conjunction with ready hydrolysis of the bitters

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solution is a characteristic property of $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ form whereas the $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ form develops a very faint colour which slowly deepens owing to gradual transformation of $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ into the $\Delta^{\beta\gamma}$ lactone. This test has given such uniform results with all of the substances studied by Jacobs and Hoffmann (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, 67, 333) that there appears to be complete justification in attributing the reduction of Tollen's reagents directly to the $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated lactone group. Although in its behaviour towards sodium nitroprusside (Jacobs and Hoffmann, *loc. cit.*) it proved to be an exception to the rule like bufagin, scillaridin and the active substance of *Convallaria majalis*; the significance of this failure to give a positive nitroprusside test cannot be evaluated in view of our meagre knowledge of the chemistry of these substances.

Corchoritin, is readily converted by strong hydrochloric acid into anhydrocorchoritin due to the removal of the hydroxyl group as water, since it no longer yields an acetyl compound.

A large number of experiments have been made with the object of degrading corchoritin to simpler products in order to determine the nature of the ring structure present. When it was oxidised with potassium permanganate in alkaline solution after saponification of the lactone group, along with oxalic acid and acetic acid and other obscure amorphous products, a syrupy non-volatile acid which was identified as pyroracemic acid, was obtained.

Corchoritin when treated with nitric acid gives carbon dioxide, oxalic acid, and a small quantity of a yellow amorphous product. When subjected to dry distillation at a high temperature it undergoes decomposition at $100-10^{\circ}/20$ mm. It gives a bright yellow brittle microcrystalline mass ($C_{12}H_{16}O_2$) and a highly fluorescent thick oil of high boiling point from which a yellow solid, m.p. 110° , was obtained.

When fused with potassium hydroxide, corchoritin gives an acid (M.W. = 183), but no other definite product could be isolated.

On pyrogenic reduction with zinc dust in a current of hydrogen, corchoritin yielded a large volume of gaseous products and a brown semi-solid distillate from which a colourless substance was isolated possessing a characteristic naphthalene-like smell. It is unsaturated, absorbs bromine, gradually turns brown in air and reacts with explosive violence with fuming nitric acid forming a nitro-derivative. It also gives an orange-red picrate, m.p. 107° . Unfortunately, the yield of this substance was extremely small and it was not possible to investigate it further.

From the above experiments certain conclusions may now be drawn with regard to the structure of corchoritin. Since corchoritin contains only one double bond, the basic hydrocarbon is $C_{12}H_{24}$. This differs from the limit hydrocarbon by two hydrogen atoms and therefore it must be a cycloparaffin or cyclic limit hydrocarbon and is composed of at least one ring. The formation of pyruvic acid by the oxidation of corchoritin proves the presence of the group

It is hoped that further experiments may throw light on the constitution of this interesting substance.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Corchoritin.—The combined resinous residue from the mother-liquor of corchorin was redissolved in alcohol and the fairly concentrated solution allowed to stand for some days. A small quantity of crystalline deposit mixed with yellowish brown gummy matter separated which was collected, washed with alcohol and dried on a porous plate. It was then extracted with hot chloroform, the operation requiring a large volume. The washed and dried extract was concentrated and was crystallised by the addition of petroleum ether, when it was obtained in aggregates of thin plates having a sulphur-yellow colour which could not be removed by recrystallisation from the above solvents. It was, however, finally obtained in pure form from dilute alcohol (50 p.c.) in the following manner.—

The substance (1.5 g.) was dissolved in 50 c.c. of hot 96 p.c. alcohol filtered several times through a bed of freshly heated active charcoal and the light yellow alcoholic filtrate was mixed with water (40 c.c.) and then warmed on the water-bath for a short time until the solution assumed a slight turbidity on cooling. It was then allowed to stand overnight. Radiating groups of lustrous prismatic needles began to separate, which were filtered, washed successively with dilute alcohol and water and dried in air (yield, 0.75 g.). It melts and effervesces at $218-20^\circ$ with preliminary sintering at 130° . The crystals are different from those of corchorin and a mixture of the two showed a considerable depression of the melting point. For this substance the name corchoritin is proposed.

Corchoritin thus obtained is also extremely bitter. The air-dried product on analysis gave results which were different from those

given by the substance dehydrated in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide at 110° or in an air-oven at 125° , the percentage of carbon being considerably lower in the former case. It was therefore inferred that the substance contains water of crystallisation. In order to verify the limit of stability of the attached water molecule, the air-dried material was first dried in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid for a week until it was of constant weight. (0.9476 g. lost 0.002 g. water; H_2O , 0.21 per cent). By this treatment the bitter changed neither its colour nor its characteristic crystalline appearance. Finally a weighed quantity of the dried material was dehydrated in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide in a toluene-bath until constant in weight with the following results:

TABLE I.

Substance taken = 0.5516 g. (dried for a week over conc. H_2SO_4).

Time of drying in hours.	Total water lost.	Percentage of water lost.
4	0.015 g.	2.71
8	0.0182	3.3

TABLE II

Substance taken = 0.4736 g. (air-dried).

2	0.011	2.3
4	0.0127	2.68
7	0.0184	3.88
10	0.0188	3.96

The material thus heated lost its crystalline structure but when heated in air-oven at $125\text{--}28^\circ$ it turned light yellow and slight decomposition appeared to have taken place, although the melting point remained unaltered. When analysed the following results were obtained.

(1) Air-dried substance, dried in vacuum over P_2O_5 at 110° (Found: H_2O , 3.96. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$, $\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires H_2O , 4.11 per cent.).

(2) Air-dried substance. (Found: C, 66.01; H, 8.8. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$, $\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires C, 65.75; H, 8.67 per cent.).

(3) Anhydrous substance. (Found: C, 68.77; H, 8.94; M. W. (cryoscopic method in glacial acetic acid), 192. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57 per cent., M. W., 210)

(4) Material dried in air-oven at 125-28° (light yellow slightly decomposed product). (Found: C, 71.3, 79.2; H, 8.25, 8.7 per cent.).

All these evidences lead to the conclusion that the compound invariably contains water of crystallisation which is very tenaciously held by the molecule and is only removed when dehydrated under reduced pressure but under the ordinary pressure the molecule suffered slight decomposition with the production of a yellow product.

The specific rotation of the anhydrous substance was observed in ethyl alcohol solution, $l = 2$; $c = 2.8912$; $\alpha_D^{27} = -2.03$; $[\alpha]_D^{27} = -35.1$.

Corchoritin is sparingly soluble in water and alcohol (50 p.c.) but readily soluble in hot chloroform, acetic acid, alcohol (95 p.c.), methyl alcohol and pyridine. It dissolves readily in cold concentrated hydrochloric acid and a yellow product is deposited on standing overnight. In glacial acetic acid it gives a beautiful red coloration with *o*-phenylenediamine and the reaction is so delicate that a trace of corchoritin can be detected by this means. It gives an intense yellow colour with ferric chloride in alcoholic solution. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with reddish-brown colour and a yellow substance separates out on the addition of water. No derivatives of corchoritin with hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine or semicarbazide could be obtained. Corchoritin contains no nitrogen, reduces Tollen's reagent (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1926, **67**, 333) in the cold, decolourises permanganate and bromine water. It gives the following colour reactions.

(1) Liebermann's "Cholestol" reaction—(cf. Lewkowitch, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1892, **11**, 44). A small quantity (0.25 g.) of the substance is dissolved in hot acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) filtered and the cold filtrate treated with a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid. It gives a transient violet pink coloration which immediately changes to beautiful deep green colour.

(2) Hagar-Salkowski reaction—(*Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1908, **57**, 385). A small quantity of the substance is dissolved by heat in glacial acetic acid (0.1 g. in 3 c.c.) filtered and the filtrate mixed with 1 c.c. chloroform and then a few drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. A brownish-yellow colour develops which changes rapidly to green.

(3) Keller-Kiliani Test—negative, Keller (*Ber. Deut. pharm., Ges.*, 1895, 5, 275). Only a brown colour is produced which changes to green when a small quantity of corchoritin is dissolved in acetic acid containing ferrous sulphate and a few drops of sulphuric acid added.

Acetylcorchoritin.—This was prepared by heating corchoritin (0.5 g.) with acetyl chloride (12 c.c.) on a water-bath for two hours. Excess of acetyl chloride was evaporated off and the product was poured into water slowly with constant stirring when a white flocculent precipitate was obtained. This was filtered, thoroughly washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol (80 p.c.), from which it is obtained in short coarse rods melting at 120-22°. It is *laevo* rotatory $[\alpha]_D^{28.5} = -6.3$. It is readily soluble in all ordinary solvents and

is free from any bitter taste. (Found: C, 66.32; H, 8.1; acetyl (Perkin's method), 17.4. $C_{14}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 66.6; H, 7.9; acetyl, 17.06 per cent.).

The *phenylurethane* of corchoritin was prepared by heating corchoritin suspended in an excess of phenylcarbamide. After half an hour a crystalline mass separated on cooling. It was washed several times with light petroleum ether and hot benzene to remove the excess of the reagent and finally recrystallised from dilute alcohol, from which it was obtained in shining plates melting at 254-66°. It was tasteless, sparingly soluble in benzene, alcohol and insoluble in light petroleum ether. The yield was very poor. (Found: N, 4.0. $C_{19}H_{23}O_4 N$ requires N, 4.25 per cent.).

Iodine Value.—The iodine value of corchoritin was determined by Wij's method. Complete absorption of iodine was observed after 24 hours' contact (I. V., 136.05) while 1 to 2 hours contact gave lower results (I. V., 124.6), but in all cases an excess of iodine was absorbed over that indicated by one double bond, (Calc. I. V., 121.0).

The brown sticky mass left in the flask after the titration with sodium thiosulphate in the second experiment was separated and dissolved in carbon tetrachloride in which it was freely soluble. On evaporating off the solvent, an orange-yellow iodo-derivative was obtained which was well-washed with sodium thiosulphate and water and crystallised from dilute acetic acid from which it was obtained in canary yellow needles melting at 150°. It was soluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and in glacial acetic acid.

Neutralisation Value of Corchoritin.—Although corchoritin is not acid to indicators, it neutralises alkalis but when saponified with al-

coholic caustic potash for a long time its titration presents difficulties owing to development of colour and decomposition.

The acid value was found to be 0·84 but on adding an excess of N/10- potassium hydroxide and allowing it to stand in the cold for two hours and titrating back, the alkali equivalent to acid value 113·4 was found to have been absorbed. In course of the titration it was found that the corchoritin solution after neutralisation with alkali gradually became deep red on standing for sometime apparently owing to the liberation of alkali. The explanation seems to be that the salt of the lactonic acid is gradually hydrolysed and the lactone is reformed liberating alkali.

Saponification Value.—This was determined by heating corchoritin with excess of 0·1N-alcoholic potash under reflux for 1 to 6 hours and titrating back the excess of alkali. Longer heating produces a dark coloured liquid which rendered titration impossible. The results are summarised in the following table.

TABLE III.

Anhydrous substance taken.	Time.	0·1N-KOH required.	Saponification value.
(1) 0·3264 g.	after 5 minutes (in the cold)	0·049 c.c.	0·84
(2) 0·3264	after 2 hours standing (in the cold)	6·6	113·4
(3) 0·4348	heated for 1 hour	12·75	164·5
(4) 0·3208	heated for 4 hours	10·15	177·5
(5) 0·2874	heated for 6 hours	10·05	196·2

The difference between the saponification and neutralisation value is very great and it thus becomes evident from the above table that it is partially converted into acid by heating with alcoholic caustic potash. Moreover, the soap solution obtained from experiment No. 3 yielded yellow amorphous product whose acid value was found to be 43·42. This proves that the lactone has been reformed to a considerable extent.

Action of Boiling Alcoholic Potash on Corchoritin.—Corchoritin (0·5 g.) was saponified by boiling in 25 c.c. of 0·1N-alkali and alcohol was evaporated off under reduced pressure and the yellow sparkling solution was acidified with acetic acid when a voluminous yellow

amorphous mass was separated. This was filtered and washed with water. The diluted filtrate on standing overnight deposited a white gelatinous mass which was collected, washed and dried in *vacuo* over concentrated sulphuric acid. The dried material was extremely hard and brittle. On recrystallisation from alcohol, it formed lustrous scales which melted with effervescence at 182°. It dissolved in methyl alcohol and less readily in alcohol and burnt with a smoky flame leaving no residue. Unlike corchoritin, the substance does not contain water of crystallisation and is tasteless but slowly develops a slight bitter taste towards the back of the tongue. It gives the Liebermann 'cholestol' reaction and in concentrated sulphuric acid develops the same red colour produced by corchoritin and it seems to be an isomeric lactone. The yield was too poor to admit of any further detailed study into the nature of the substance. (Found: C, 68·81 ; H, 8·75. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68·57 ; H, 8·57 per cent.).

The yellow residue dissolved in alkali from which it could be precipitated by acid. Attempts to crystallise the substance from various solvents were unsuccessful. A portion of the yellow substance when warmed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the product filtered through a bed of animal charcoal deposited a white crystalline substance which was found to be identical with corchoritin.

Action of Sodium Ethylate on Corchoritin.—Sodium (0·5 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and corchoritin (0·5 g.) was added to the mixture. It dissolved with a red colour which gradually changed to brown. After heating for 4 hours on a sand-bath the product was poured in ice-water and 2 c.c. of ice-cooled glacial acetic acid were added. A yellowish-brown gelatinous precipitate separated, which was collected, washed and dried. When purified from dilute alcohol it was obtained as a deep yellow amorphous powder melting with decomposition at 208° with preliminary softening at 185°. It was tasteless and dissolved in alkali when warmed. The neutralised filtrate was extremely bitter to the taste showing that the reaction was not complete. It shows that isomeric change has taken place but attempts to isolate any crystalline substance from the highly coloured product were unsuccessful.

Anhydro-corchoritin.—Corchoritin (1·39 g.) dissolved at the ordinary temperature in hydrochloric acid (30 c.c., *d* 1·19). Solution readily occurred with a pink colour which gradually changed to dirty green. After about 15 minutes crystals began to separate. After

several hours the substance was collected and washed thoroughly with hot water until free from acid. It was then allowed to crystallise slowly from its ethereal solution in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid in lustrous light yellow flakes, m. p. 97° (decomp.). It dissolved in almost all organic solvents. Attempts to acetylate, benzoylate and to prepare a phenylurethane derivative of the substance in the usual manner resulted in the recovery of the unchanged material. (Found: C, 74.78; H, 8.5; M.W., 180. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 75.00; H, 8.33 per cent., M.W., 192).

The following experiment shows that the conversion of corchoritin into anhydro-corchoritin is quantitative. Corchoritin was dissolved in 10 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (d 1.19) and allowed to stand overnight in a corked flask. It was then diluted with 20 c.c. of water and heated under reflux. After 4 hours it was filtered through a weighed Gooch crucible, washed till free from acid and dried to constant weight in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid [0.4779 g. gave 0.4050 g. anhydro-compound (insoluble) = 84.7 per cent.]. A further quantity (m.p. 98° decomp.) of 2.42 per cent. was isolated from the yellow filtrate by extracting with ether, thus giving a total yield of 87.12 per cent. ($C_{12}H_{18}O_3$, $\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires H_2O , 87.6 per cent.).

The filtrate was neutralised and treated with the combined carbonate-citrate reagent [Shaffer and Hartmann (micro-method), *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, 45, 365] but only a trace of reducing sugar was obtained.

Action of Cold Concentrated Hydrochloric Acid on Corchoritin.— Finely powdered corchoritin (1 g.) was added to 30 c.c. of cooled hydrochloric acid (d 1.19). At first a portion of the substance separated but soon redissolved completely with a dirty green colour. The mixture was then kept overnight in contact with ice in a closed vessel. The dark yellow substance which separated was collected, washed with ice-cold hydrochloric acid and dried in a vacuum over solid caustic potash for 4 days when it was found to be free from adhering hydrochloric acid. The product was obtained in an amorphous condition, having in mass a greenish-yellow appearance. It was then purified from chloroform by the addition of petroleum ether in microcrystalline condition (yield, 0.7 g.). The melting point was not satisfactory and it shrank at 68° and decomposed at 90°. The results of analysis, obtained were not satis-

factory after repeated trials. This is probably attributed to the admixture with the anhydro-compound. (Found: Cl, 13·2).

The mother-liquor could be almost completely precipitated by dilution with water and the material obtained in this way was found to be anhydro-corchoritin.

Distillation of Corchoritin with Hydrochloric Acid (12 p.c.).—When corchoritin (0·5 g.) was distilled with 12 p.c. hydrochloric acid (120 c.c.) according to the method of Willstätter at 130-60° in a glycerinebath, it changed into a yellow resinous product and the distillate gave no tests for furfural or methyl furfural by means of phloroglucinol. The aqueous-acid solution in the distilling flask on neutralisation and concentration yielded (i) a small quantity of a yellow product soluble in ether, (ii) did not reduce Fehling's solution, (iii) did not react with phenylhydrazine, the absence of glucose thus being indicated.

Action of o-Phenylenediamine on Corchoritin.—Corchoritin (0·42 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) and heated for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with o-phenylenediamine hydrochloride (0·5 g.). A blood red coloration was produced. The mixture was concentrated and allowed to stand for several days but no crystalline substance separated. On pouring the red solution in a large volume of water a red precipitate was produced which was collected and purified from methyl alcohol as red powder which melted with decomposition at 130-42° and the product contains nitrogen. It could not be obtained sufficiently pure for analysis.

Fusion with Potassium Hydroxide.—Corchoritin (5 g.) was gradually added to potassium hydroxide (70 g.) and water (7 c.c.) at 120°; a vigorous reaction took place with much frothing and evolution of inflammable gases. The mass was finally heated at 200-20° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The cold melt was dissolved in water, acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with water and extracted three times with a strong solution of sodium bicarbonate. The sodium bicarbonate extract was concentrated and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid when a sticky yellowish-brown mass separated which was again extracted with ether, dried and the ether evaporated. The brown mass thus obtained had a strong fatty odour. The analysis of its silver salt gave 183 (approx.) as the molecular weight (0·247 g. silver salt gave 0·092 g. Ag; taking it to be monobasic M.W., 182·9). It was not obtained in sufficient quantity for further examination.

The aqueous mother-liquor after extraction with ether contained oxalic acid (isolated as calcium salt).

The dark brown insoluble residue left after all these operations had a strong naphthalene-like odour but nothing definite could be isolated from the mass by repeated attempts at crystallisation.

Attempts at Reduction of Corchoritin by Zinc and Acetic Acid.—Zinc dust in small quantities was added to boiling solution of corchoritin (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid solution (25 c.c.) and the mixture heated for 3 hours. After filtrating from unchanged zinc dust, the filtrate was diluted with water when a colourless substance deposited slowly on standing in aggregates of nodular crystals which proved on examination to be the unchanged corchoritin.

Dihydrocorchoritin.—A solution of corchoritin (1 g.) in 30 c.c. of dilute methyl alcohol was hydrogenated by electrolytic hydrogen in presence of 5 c.c. of 1 p.c. palladium chloride and 15 c.c. of 2 p.c. gum arabic. In about 6 hours approximately 1 molecular equivalent of hydrogen was absorbed, after which the metal separated as a precipitate and absorption of hydrogen ceased. The mixture was evaporated to dryness and the residue was extracted with chloroform. The glassy residue from the chloroform extract was repeatedly extracted with cold absolute alcohol. The combined extract was concentrated and addition of water in the solution produced a white precipitate which was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colourless needles, melting at 191°. It is tasteless and does not reduce Tollen's reagent nor absorbs bromine in chloroform solution showing that the double bond had been hydrogenated. (Found: C, 67.57; H, 9.51. $C_{12}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 67.9 H, 9.4 per cent.). The same substance was obtained by reducing corchoritin in methyl alcoholic solution with sodium amalgam but the yield was very poor.

Action of Heat on Corchoritin.—When corchoritin (0.2 g.) was heated in a hard test tube at 220° in a glycerine-bath, it melted with effervescence and did not turn baryta milky but on raising the temperature, the substance gradually turned brown and carbon dioxide being evolved turned baryta milky. The substance partly sublimed to a yellow mass and a brown sticky liquid was found in the tube, which on cooling became hard and transparent. It was devoid of bitter taste and dissolved in oil of turpentine with a yellow colour. With acetic anhydride and concentrated sulphuric acid it first gave a fugitive reddish-brown colour which immediately changed to green and finally yellow on standing.

Distillation under Reduced Pressure.—Corchoritin (5 g.) was distilled at 20 mm. in a small distilling flask. The temperature was raised slowly, and there was much evolution of gas and a sulphur-yellow liquid came over between 90° and 110°, which condensed as a crystalline mass in the receiver. A strongly fluorescent oil having a very high boiling point was left in the distilling flask which solidified on cooling to a hard brittle resinous mass from which a yellow solid, m.p. 110°, was obtained by shaking the ethereal extract of the resin with caustic soda.

The sublimate was collected and on examination was found to be the anhydro-corchoritin.

Pyrogenic Reduction with Zinc Dust.—Corchoritin (5 g.) was distilled with zinc dust in the usual way in a stream of hydrogen. Gaseous products were evolved. The results of examination are recorded in Table IV. The brown distillate which was collected in the receiver, cooled in a freezing mixture consisted of a mixture of solid and liquid having a strong naphthalene-like odour which turned deep brown on standing in air. The liquid was absorbed in a porous plate and the crude product decolourised potassium permanganate, absorbed bromine in carbon tetrachloride solution and dissolved in fuming nitric acid with explosive violence. The solid crystallised from alcohol yielded a very small quantity of glistening colourless needles melting at 135°. It yielded an orange-red picrate, m.p. 107°. On nitration with fuming nitric acid, it yielded a yellow compound, probably a nitro-derivative, which when purified from acetic acid, melted with effervescence at 150°. (Found: N, 10.35 per cent).

TABLE IV

Total volume of gas collected = 460 c.c. out of which 60 c.c. were analysed and the results gave the mean of several experiments.

Gas.	Volume in c.c.	Per cent.
Carbon dioxide	2.8	4.66
Hydrocarbon (C _n H _{2n})	1.0	1.66
Oxygen	1.4	2.31
Carbonmonoxide	4.8	8.00
Methane	1.4	2.31
Hydrogen	48.6	81.00
	60.00	99.94

Action of Oxidising Agents on Corchoritin.

(a) *Alkaline potassium permanganate.*—A solution of 0.73 g. of the substance in 30 c.c. *N/2*-alcoholic caustic potash was refluxed for four hours. The soap solution after distilling off the alcohol under reduced pressure was treated with 150 c.c. of 3 per cent. potassium permanganate. Oxidation occurred slowly in the cold with gradual deposition of manganese dioxide. The solution was filtered, concentrated to a small volume and when acidified it yielded no solid product. The whole was repeatedly shaken with ether and the ethereal solution was washed, dried and on evaporation, yielded a glassy viscous mass having an acid smell of acetic acid, which did not solidify even on standing over sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator for a month. It was purified by redissolving in ammonia, acidifying and extracting with ether. It had a strong acid reaction on litmus and its neutral solution did not give any coloration with ferric chloride and did not react with acetic anhydride or acetyl chloride. It reduced Fehling's solution promptly and gave a positive iodoform reaction with alkaline iodine solution depositing iodoform on standing. It was readily identified as pyruvic acid through its *p*-nitrophenylhydrazone m. p. 220°. The aqueous mother-liquor after extraction with ether contained oxalic acid (isolated as calcium salt).

(b) *Dilute nitric acid.*—0.5 G. of the substance and 5 c.c. of nitric acid (*d* 1.36) were taken in a boiling tube provided with a delivery tube that dipped in a clear baryta water. The whole was heated on a water-bath at 60°. The baryta turned turbid gradually and deposited barium carbonate and the reaction mixture gradually turned yellow. After six hours, it was poured in a beaker and slowly heated on the water-bath, adding water from time to time and with an occasional shaking. A deep yellow solution was obtained, which was extracted with ether. The washed and dried ethereal solution on evaporation deposited a yellow viscous mass which on standing partially solidified to a beautiful crystalline mass. Almost colourless needles were collected, washed with a little water and on examination they were found to be oxalic acid. The yellow gummy mass could not be identified owing to the small quantity of the substance available.

(c) *Kiliani-chromic acid solution.*—A solution of the substance (0.7 g) in acetic acid (10 c.c.) was treated with 3 c.c. of Kiliani-chromic acid solution. Oxidation was prompt and after five minutes

the mixture which contained excess of the reagent, was diluted with water and the whole allowed to stand overnight when an unidentified yellow acid gradually separated. It could not be crystallised from the ordinary solvents, in which it was insoluble. It decomposed with charring at 240° with preliminary sintering at 215°. The substance could not be obtained sufficiently pure for analysis.

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